

Effects of Computerized Financial System on Financial Performance of Public Companies

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Abstract:

The main purpose of the paper was to establish the effect of the computerized financial system on financial performance of parastatals. The study adopted descriptive survey design. This study is based on the Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology UTAUT. The study took a census of 118 Parastatal found in Nairobi town. Data were collected using questionnaires. The data to be collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings showed that Perceived usefulness, the Competent computerized financial system had a significant positive effect on financial performance. However, the Perceived cost had a significant negative effect on financial performance. Therefore, in order for firms to complete their auditing tasks more quickly, they need to embrace the use of the computerized financial system

Keywords: *Computerized Financial System, Financial Performance, Perceived Usefulness, Competent Computerized Financial System, Perceived Cost*

Introduction

Today's modern technology brought into use the computer, this technology is the application of science to the gathering, recording, processing and communicating business information by means of electronic media. Most common tool for application is the computer, and it involves all the transaction processing system management information system various business support system, etc. The computer is a central force in the advancement of various organizations

Various studies by BIS, (2007), have argued that increased financial integration which is evident in the foreign exchange market. The principal element that "integrates" a computerized financial system is a common, single, reliable platform database (or a series of interconnected databases) to and from which all data expressed in financial terms flow up to including service delivery sectors. Various scholars have argued that integration is the key to any successful computerized financial system. In a nutshell, integration implies that the system which is designed to surpass desired service delivery goals.

The computerized financial system can enable prompt and efficient access to reliable financial data and help strengthen government financial controls, improving the provision of government services, raising the budget process to higher levels of transparency and accountability, and expediting government operations. Financial management systems through projects that provide a combination of technical assistance, training, financial resources and procurement support to service delivery firms

According to McBride (2000), computerized packages can quickly generate all types of reports needed by management for instance budget analysis and variance analysis. Data processing and analysis are faster and more accurate which meets the managers need for accurate and timely information for decision making. In addition, Indira (2008) pronounced the improvement in business performance. As result computerization of the financial systems as it is a highly integrated application that transforms the business processes with the performance-enhancing features which encompass accounting, inventory control, reporting and statutory processes. He then says, this helps the company access information faster and takes quicker decisions as it also enhances communication.

McBride (2000) stated that managers could not easily satisfy statutory and donor reporting requirements such as profit and loss account, balance sheet and customized reporting without using computerized accounting systems. With the system in place, this can be done quickly and with less effort. Computerized financial systems ease auditing and have better access to required information such as cheque numbers, payments, and other transactions which help to reduce the time needed to provide this type of information and documentation during auditing.

The Government of Kenya has made great strides in the implementation of e-government in most of its Departments. This has significantly contributed to efficiency in the delivery of services. Processes which previously had several steps are now completed instantaneously. There is quick access to information which was previously difficult and time-consuming. This is because large databases with networked access have been created. Thus the implementation of ICT systems in the public sector has facilitated faster delivery of services. This is achieved through enhanced communication to staff and clients.

In Kenya, Computerization of financial transaction in some government institutions is being hampered by the resistance of some officials. This is because many organizations do not take their employees through the change process to allay the fear of computerization. There is also fear of losing jobs because certain tasks can be performed by fewer staff after computerization. As such in most organizations computerization exists hand in hand with manual operations.

Introduction of Information Technology into the public sector has provided new challenges. Furthermore, the shift into IT in the Public Sector has brought about profound opportunities for corruption. Introducing new technologies quickly for functional and fiscal purposes implies that risk assessment and control with regard to e-corruption is not adequate. Lack of installing proper controls and adequate safeguards in the computer systems has provided greater opportunities to IT – literate staff to engage in electronic malpractices.

In managing an organization and implementing an internal control system the role of the computerized financial system is crucial. An important question in the field of accounting and management decision-making concerns the fit of the computerized financial system with organizational requirements for information communication and control. At Kenya Seed Company, new computer systems are developed to meet a variety of company needs, i.e., meeting new legal requirements, maintaining or enhancing profitability, improving efficiency and to reducing costs. However, there has been lack of good financial systems creating doubts about efficiency and effectiveness of management in public sector. Previous studies have shown that computer fraud and abuse can have a detrimental effect on an organizations performance. In addition, these studies have given much attention to computerized accounting systems with less few of the addressing the issues of computerized financial systems in relation to firm performance. This study, therefore, will attempt to find a various aspect of computerized financial system affect company performance.

H₀₁: Perceived usefulness of computerized financial system has no significant effect on company performance

H₀₂: the Competent computerized financial system has no significant effect on company performance

H₀₂: the Perceived cost of the computerized financial system has no significant effect on company performance

Theoretical review

Prior accounting research has used information systems theoretical frameworks to predict acceptance (or adoption) of accounting technology (e.g., Walsh and White 2000; Bedard et al. 2003; West and Davis 2008). Several theoretical frameworks exist to predict acceptance of new technology (Davis 1989; Ajzen 1991; Moore and Benbasat 1991). This study will use the Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology UTAUT (Venkatesh et al. 2003) because it incorporates elements of several prominent information systems

models/theories that predict usage including technology acceptance model (TAM) (Davis 1989), theory of planned behavior (Ajzen 1991; Taylor and Todd 1995), innovation diffusion theory (Moore and Benbasat 1991), and social cognitive theory (Compeau and Higgins 1995). Furthermore, the UTAUT has been shown to explain up to 70 percent of the variance in intention to use technology, outperforming each of the aforementioned specified models (Venkatesh et al. 2003).

Researchers have identified the following common environmental factors relating to IT adoption (and specifically the adoption of Internet technologies): pressure from competitors, customers or suppliers; the role of government (incentives); partners' alliances; technological infrastructure; technology consultants; image of Internet technology; and users' expectations (Aguila – Obra and Padilla – Melendez, 2006). Technological factors include complexity, compatibility, relative advantage, ease of use and usefulness (Davis, 1989) & Rogers, 1983). The technological factors are related to barriers to technology adoption and its perceived benefits. The perceived benefits for managers could be direct, such as cost savings or income generation, or indirect, such as potential opportunities in new markets, marketing, or publicity (Poon and Swatman, 1999). Thus, when adopting an innovation, organizations must perceive the positive effects of the adoption- and hence its potential value- before starting the process (Vadapalli and Ramamurthy, 1997). The organizational factors that have been mostly cited in literature include: IT users' community; organizational structure; firm's processes; firm size; technological capabilities of the organization's members; the technological and financial resources available; the culture of the organization; process of selecting and implementing the IT; management backing and support for the project; and the project leader (Aguila- Obra& Padilla – Melendez, 2006). Some researchers have integrated these factors into one model (Kamal, 2006; Kuan&Chau, 2001; Mehrtens, Cragg& Mills, 2001) allowing for the treatment of all these factors and their interaction in one dynamic framework. Such framework can explain marked differences in the performance of organizations in identical contextual situations (Montealegre, 1996).

The concept and process of the Computerized financial system have become of increasing importance as its career development advantages have become more widely known. The computerized financial system is under computerized accounting documents, e-books, e-statements and to adapt to the way computerized system of internal controls audit work carried out, mainly including computerized accounting system, auditing, data authenticity, the legitimacy of the audit, as well as computerized accounting system processing and control functions auditing. Computerization in the accounting process, due to tools, storage media, accounts processing, an internal control system with manual methods are different, making the computerized audit work is facing many new problems.

The computerized financial system can help task complexity on the accuracy of financial judgment (Dowling and Leech, 2007). The financial judgment demonstrates that memory; knowledge, learning, cognition, and other mental processes of individuals play a significant part in the overall judgmental processes and affect their judgment and decision performance (Nelson, Ratliff, et al., 2003). Hence, computerized financial system competency may lead to good financial judgment. Additionally, financial judgment is affected by several external and internal environmental factors which influence its operations and practices such time pressure (Maule, Hockey, et al., 2000).

Empirical review

Perceived Usefulness of Computerized financial system On Company Performance

Perceived usefulness has been defined as a person's subjective perception of the effortlessness of a computer system, which affects their perceived usefulness thus having an indirect effect on user's technology acceptance. It is defined as 'the degree to which a person believes that using a particular technology will enhance his or her job performance' Davis (1986). In the words of Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw (1992),

perceived usefulness refers to consumers' perceptions regarding the outcome of the experience. Pikkarainen et al., (2004), found that perceived usefulness of a computerized financial information system was the most influential factor in determining its usage. It was found that users had a significantly strong relation with usage, greater than that between perceived ease of use and usage (Guriting and Ndubusi, 2006).

William et al., (2005) in his study argues that computerized financial accounting systems are of several importance to companies. Systems for small and medium-sized businesses can be purchased off the shelf at low cost. These programs allow managers to see the company's financial position in real-time and make adjustments to the business strategy as needed which poses a great deal towards high firm performance. Computerized systems can also provide instant reports on stock evaluation, profit and loss, customer accounts and payroll and sales analysis, again, allowing faster adjustments in your business strategy. In addition, transactions need to be input only once, and, with some training, anyone in the company can handle the inputting.

Using a computerized accounting system can save time and thus the firm performance is increased. Computerized financial system software allows faster data entry than manual accounting, and allows documents such as invoices, purchase orders, and payroll to be collated and printed quickly and accurately. Because of its efficiency and ease of use, computerized accounting systems also allow one to improve inventory control and payment collection, saving time and improving cash flow. Because computerized systems update some records automatically, the companies' account records will always be up to date, saving time in updating thus improvement of the firm financial performance. (Balachandher et al., 2001)

Computerized financial accounting system processes the financial transactions and events to produce accurate accounting results as per the user requirements or guidelines. Every proper accounting system, be it manual or computerized must follow the generally accepted accounting principles and also the framework for maintenance of records and generation of reports must be well defined and easy to be understood hence improving company performance. (Joppe, 2000)

Perceived usefulness explains the user's perception to the extent that the technology will improve the user's workplace performance Davis., et al., (1989). This means that the user has a perception of how useful the technology is in performing his job tasks. This includes decreasing the time for doing the job, more efficiency and accuracy.

Shin (2010) found that perceived benefit has an influence on user acceptance of the computerized financial system. Kumar and Ravindran (2012) stated that perceived usefulness represent cognitive beliefs formed via second-hand information and so satisfaction was found to be a stronger predictor of continuance intention; there is a significant effect of perceived usefulness on the intention to use computerized financial system (Wang *et al.*, 2003). Dass and Pal (2011) found a positive effect on demand and adoption of the computerized financial system from perceived usefulness predictor. Perceived usefulness has a positive relationship in examining the intention to adopt a computerized financial system in Malaysia (Cheah *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, it was hypothesized that perceived usefulness of computerized financial system has no significant effect on the performance of a firm.

Competent computerized financial system and performance

Competent accounting information management is also one of the key components of computerized financial system competency that helps auditor's report have to reason fully documented. Computerized financial system competency requires reliable and accurate information about the area of care being investigated. The firm needs to have an effective data collection strategy in place before it starts collecting data for auditing (Choe, 2004). Nothing is more frustrating than spending precious time collecting data to find that it is not what you wanted or

collecting too much information that is unused. The firm need to ensure that there is collect the correct information to meet auditing objectives and auditor's information is collected accurately and timely (Andon, Chong, et al., 2010).

Competent computerized accounting systems help businesses in their accounting processes and reporting thus creating a high financial performance in companies. Each system may be different, but the goal of competent computerized financial and accounting systems is to help a business be more efficient and effective in its financial matters thus increasing performance. If planning to purchase a new computerized accounting system, the more it competent and accurate it is, the better off the company is in its financial performance.(Yasuharu, 2003)

Competent accounting information systems collect and processes transaction data and communicate financial information to decision makers. It handles all steps in the accounting cycle accurately. Documents that provide evidence of transactions are provided accurately to ensure overall performance of companies.(Evans, 1999)

Competent financial information management refers to the process of combining the financial information in a convenient way which makes it easier to manage data and can be recovered or regained by firms whenever needed (Knechel, 2007). Talking about data, these are essential in every minute of the business run. It becomes a necessity for all firms to manage their precious data. Looking at the cost and other factors, these firms prefer data management companies to manage their data (Zambon and Zan, 2000).

Therefore, this study defines the meaning of competent financial information management that it is the set of processes and technologies that support the collection, managing, and publishing of information with providing information to clients by preparing, analyzing, and verifying financial documents (Gil, Berenguer et al., 2008).

Computerized financial system competency is assigned an important role in the design and operation of the best of fraud detective. For analytical procedures by computer to be beneficial in enabling an auditor to effectively assess the risk of financial statement fraud, an auditor must possess the relevant computerized financial system knowledge and skill required to uncover the fraud if it is present and the ability to trigger or activate, that computerized financial system knowledge and skill when needed (Lee and Kim, 2009). An individual cue within the financial statements may trigger the auditor's fraud knowledge if it is material enough. Or, it may be necessary for a manager to identify several cues to trigger auditors' fraud knowledge. Financial statement fraud involves an attempt by management to fool the clients (Stalebrink and Sacco, 2007). One way to try to hide the fraud is with a series of manipulations of accounts, none of which is material enough on its own to trigger the auditor's suspicion of fraud.

Perceive Cost Of Computerized Financial System And Firms Performance

Price/cost is one of the single most important factors that influence the consumer adoption of innovation (Alam *et al.*, 2009). Cost factor may consist of the initial purchase price (handset fee), ongoing usage cost (subscription fee, fee service, and communication fee), maintenance cost and upgrade cost (Luarn and Lin, 2005). Perceived financial cost (PCF) with reference to the adoption of the computerized financial system relates to the cost of availing the services to customers, time-saving subscription fees. Therefore, the lower the transaction charges as well as subscription fees, the higher the rate of adoption.

Pagani (2004) stated that price or cost factor was one of the main determinants of Computerized Financial System. Anil *et al.*, (2003) also stated that cost is one of the factors influencing the adoption of computerized financial System in Singapore state corporations . In addition, Wei *et al.*, (2009) argued that perceived cost is one of the barriers that prevent Malaysian government from using m-commerce.

Kimenyi and Ndung'u (2009) argued that the rapid growth of the computerized financial system in Kenya is evidenced by the great need for low-cost financial services. The introduction of the computerized financial system has really changed how people can transact businesses because they need not go to their bank premises. This has resulted in the flexibility of carrying out several transactions at any time anywhere, thus, time and cost saving. In addition to that, Ng'weno (2010) argued that computerized financial system provides a secure alternative to transact a large amount of cash, as well as time-saving cost and people, can also pay for their electricity bills within moments without traveling to the offices. marowczynski and Pickens (2009) found that urban users of Computerized Financial System adopted it because it is cheaper than any other money transfer options.

Transaction speed saves customers' time especially with the introduction of new technologies. The more customers understand the speed of transactions among other factors, the more positive the attitude will be into the use of mobile banking services (Beiginia *et al.*, 2011). Poon (2007) found that 89 percent of the respondents agreed that the prices of internet connection were affordable and reasonable, 22 percent strongly agreed that a negligible transaction service fee is charged and also 70 percent agreed that the fees charged for the service is acceptable.

The costs of computerized financial systems should be sufficiently flexible to meet the resulting changes in the demands made upon it. This will ensure that the software to be used in these firms is affordable hence will enable firms to use the best accounting systems improving firm performance. (Idowu *et al.*, 2002)

Computerization of financial systems requires some amount of financial commitment with a great deal of managerial and technological expertise needed at the very beginning of the installation process in order to launch a successful venture. There is the need to assess the cost-benefit effects that will help in carefully weighing the two so as to know the benefits to be derived from it since, in the end, the main focus will be on the benefits which will improve firm performance. (Schmalensee, 1999)

Material and methods

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The design is considered appropriate as it enabled the researcher to reach many subjects within a limited time (Kothari, 2005). The study took a census of 118 Parastatal found in Nairobi town (GoK, 2012). The unit of analysis will be 2 supply chain managers giving a total of 236 respondents. The 118 Parastatal are adequate for this study because Saunders *et al.*, (2000) argue that a minimum of 10 units are adequate for surveys. Therefore 118 Parastatal are above the minimum accepted units for surveys. In pursuit of the study to achieve its objectives, the research instrument to be used as structured questionnaires containing both open and closed-ended questions. The test re-test method will be used to obtain the two scores which were correlated using the Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient and the Cronbach's alpha to establish the reliability of the instruments. The data to be collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was include frequencies, percentages, and means while inferential statistics will include the ANOVA and regression analysis. The multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis.

Results

In this section, the data was analyzed and discussed accordingly and in relation to the objectives of the study. The researcher considered it important to establish the perceived usefulness of the computerized financial system. The results are as shown below: mean of 3.7203, skewness -0.943 and kurtosis of 0.055, this concludes that perceived usefulness of computerized financial system was high in the company. The average mean summed up to 3.1363; skewness 0.25 and a negative kurtosis of -1,351 showed that respondents were generally

impartial in relation to the competent computerized financial system. However, Perceived cost of computerized financial systems company performance. The result is shown below: The average mean summed up to 3.7203; skewness -0.943 and a negative kurtosis of 0.055 showed that respondents were in agreement in relation to the competent computerized financial system. Pearson Correlations results in table 1 showed that perceived usefulness of computerized financial system was most highly positively and significantly correlated with company performance ($r=0.608$, $p<0.05$). Thus perceived the usefulness of computerized financial system had 60.8% positive relationship with company performance. The competent computerized financial system was the second component to be positively related with company performance ($r = 0.627$, $p<0.05$) an indication that competent computerized financial system had 62.7% significant positive relationship with company performance. Fraud detective of the computerized audit was also positively and significantly associated with company performance as shown by $r = 0.542$, $p<0.05$ implying that fraud detective of the computerized audit had 54.2% positive relationship with company performance. Also perceived the cost of the computerized financial system was highly and positively correlated with company performance ($r = 0.559$, $p<0.05$). The perceived cost of the computerized financial system had 55.9% significant positive relationship with company performance. Findings provided enough evidence to suggest that there was a linear relationship between perceived usefulness of the computerized financial system, competent computerized financial system, fraud detective of computerized audit and perceived cost of the computerized financial system with company performance.

Table 1 Correlation Statistics

	Mean	Skewness	Company Performance	Perceived usefulness of the computerized financial system	competent computerized financial system	The perceived cost of the computerized financial system
Company Performance	3.7203	-0.943	1			
Perceived usefulness of computerized financial system	3.7203	-0.943	.608**	1		
competent computerized financial system	3.1363	0.25	.627**	.490**	1	
Perceived cost of computerized financial system	3.7367	-0.178	.559**	.436**	.608**	1

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

Hypothesis testing

Table 2 illustrates the model summary of multiple regression models; the results showed that all the three predictors (perceived usefulness of the computerized financial system, perceived the cost of the computerized financial system and competent computerized financial system) explained 54.7 percent variation of company performance. This showed that considering the four study independent variables, there is a probability of predicting company performance by 54.7% ($R^2 = 0.547$). Study findings in ANOVA table 2 indicated that the above-discussed coefficient of determination was significant as evidence of F ratio of 47.039 with p-value $0.000 < 0.05$ (level of significance). Thus, the model was fit to predict company performance using perceived usefulness of the computerized financial system, perceived the cost of the computerized financial system, competent computerized financial system and fraud detective of the computerized audit. Table 2 shows that the values of tolerance were greater than 0.2 rule and those of VIF was less than 4. This shows lack of

multicollinearity among independent variables. It, therefore, omitting variables with insignificant regression coefficients, would be inappropriate.

Hypothesis 1 (H_{01}) revealed that there is no relationship between perceived usefulness of computerized financial system and company performance. Findings showed that perceived usefulness of computerized financial system had coefficients of the estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_1 = 0.356$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) implying that we reject the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between perceived usefulness of computerized financial system and company performance. Thus, the research findings are in agreement with Wei *et al.*, (2009) study on auditor's intention to use computers in Malaysia which found perceived usefulness as the most significant determinant to predict auditor's intention to use computers. Similarly, Viehland and Leong (2007) study on acceptance and use of computerized financial system found that 59% of New Zealand respondents perceived the computerized financial system to be useful or very useful. However, a comparative study that was conducted in USA, Russia, and China by Vatanparast and Qadim (2009) on firm's intention to use computerized financial system found that perceived usefulness and behavioral intention was supported in China and Russia only. Therefore, perceived usefulness on behavioral intention happens to be different in different countries Cognate to the study findings, Kumar and Ravindran (2012) stated that perceived usefulness represent cognitive beliefs formed via second-hand information and so satisfaction was found to be a stronger predictor of continuance intention. Further, Wang *et al.*, (2003) found a significant effect of perceived usefulness on the intention to use the computerized financial system. Similarly, in examining the intention to adopt a computerized financial system in Malaysia, perceived usefulness was found to have a positive relationship with the adoption of the computerized financial system (Cheah *et al.*, 2011).

Hypothesis 2 (H_{02}) stated that there is no relationship between the competent computerized financial system and company performance. Findings showed that competent computerized financial system had coefficients of the estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_2 = 0.272$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) which indicates that we reject the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the competent computerized financial system and company performance. This implies that for each unit increase in the competent computerized financial system, there is up to 0.272 unit increase in company performance. According to Knechel, (2007), the competent computerized financial system is basically combining information in a convenient way making it easier to manage data and recovery whenever needed. Further, competent accounting information management is designed specifically for auditing and ensures that only the relevant information required for the audit is collected. According to Bushman and Smith, (2001), auditors have to ensure that the financial information is unambiguous especially when they have several people collecting data, to prevent each person interpreting the form differently. Cognate to study findings, Benford and Hunton, (2000) assert that competent accounting information management has effluence on audit judgment since accuracy and confidence help the judgment of auditor get well soon. Therefore, competent accounting has a positive relationship with company performance.

Hypothesis3 (H_{03}) stated that there is no relationship between the perceived cost of the computerized financial system and company performance. Findings showed that perceived cost of the computerized financial system had coefficients of the estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_4 = 0.15$ (p-value = 0.011 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) which implies that we reject the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between the perceived cost of the computerized financial system and company performance. This implies that there is up to 0.15 unit increase in company performance for each unit increase in the perceived cost of the computerized financial system. The effect of the perceived cost of the computerized financial system is more than 2 times the effect attributed to the error; this is indicated by the t-test value = 2.573.

Table 2 Multiple Regression Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.605	0.19		3.178	0.002		
Perceived usefulness	0.342	0.047	0.356	7.269	0.000	0.729	1.372
Competent computerized financial system	0.318	0.07	0.272	4.528	0.000	0.484	2.067
Perceived cost	0.154	0.06	0.15	2.573	0.011	0.515	1.944
R Square	0.547						
Adjusted R Square	0.54						
F	47.039						
Sig.	.000b						

a Dependent Variable: Company performance

Conclusion And Recommendation

In conclusion, having computerized financial system saves time, frustration and saves on cost. Through the computerized financial system, it is possible for firms to safeguard their assets by instituting effective internal controls. The computerized financial system not only meets this requirement but also gives the firm facts it needs to make important decisions. Further, fraud detective of computerized-audit ensures that high standards of security and control are maintained to minimize the potential impact on the organization. Additionally, it reinforces the firm's attitude to risk. Therefore, an auditor must possess the relevant computerized-audit knowledge and skill required to uncover the fraud if it is present. On top of that, computerized financial system aids budgeting. It, therefore, sets a firm apart from its competitors and is an essential tool for a company.

Therefore, in order for firms to complete their auditing tasks more quickly, they need to embrace the use of the computerized financial system. Also, through the computerized financial system, efficiency and effectiveness in auditing are enhanced and auditing task 24 hours per day is possible. Further, for firms to know the state of their accounts they need to use the computerized financial system. In order for firms to improve their accuracy and skills, there is need to adopt a computerized financial system. Further, the computerized financial system also makes the decision making the process faster. Thus firms should gather relevant knowledge and resources in regards to the computerized financial system so that there is more ownership of decisions made.

Finally, study findings reveal that perceived cost of the computerized financial system has a significant effect on company performance. Therefore, in order to have a low transaction, reduce operation cost and save on time, use of the computerized financial system should be enhanced.

This study has established the effect of the computerized financial system on organization performance of public firms. This study recommends that another study should be done to augment finding in this study; it, therefore, recommends a study be done on the effect of the computerized financial system on auditor's independence.

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